

Introduction and conclusion and their importance in scientific research

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Introduction to Research: Its Importance and Key Elements

The introduction of a research paper or thesis is one of the most prominent elements that must be present in a solid scientific study. It acts as the research's facade and the reader's first stop. Through it, many readers can get a comprehensive impression of the study's content and substance, as well as the writer's orientations and inclinations, and the elements of their research are easily revealed to the good reader – on condition that the writer is proficient in their study and topic. Therefore, the introduction must be well-written and organized, encompassing all the components of the idea that the study entails.

Some introductions serve as the first and last stop for many readers, as the writer has already met all the criteria for comprehensive writing, and the introduction of their research contains the complete idea of their topic. Overall, it is a primary and necessary step in writing a scientific research paper. Without it, the research cannot appear in the correct form, or at least in a form befitting any paper that can be called a complete scientific paper.

The introduction is defined as a comprehensive and complete summary of the components of a scientific paper or research. It is a complementary part of

the elements of the scientific study. In it, the researcher deals with generalities, leaving the details for the text. This is a task that is almost not easy for researchers and beginners, as it requires multiple readings of previous studies that have dealt with the same topic that the writer or researcher is working on. This is done to enable them to study the aspects of the general idea of their topic and thus mature the content and terminology used within the research, while avoiding excessive length and verbosity in defining their topic, as excessive length in writing the introduction is considered by many to be one of the common mistakes in writing a scientific paper.

The introduction may also be random and does not include the main ideas of the research topic, meaning that it does not include a logical and organized sequence of the main elements of the introduction. Therefore, it is a guide or a roadmap, as some call it, for the reader or the person who looks at the scientific paper, and it is in the form of organized and sequential points.

1. Reasons for Choosing the Research Topic:

Informing the reader about the reasons that prompted the writer to choose the research idea is a means of persuasion.

Through it, the researcher can direct the reader's thinking towards reading the study from beginning to end.

Of course, this depends on the writer's ability to present objective and logical reasons in a seasoned scientific style.

It is not scientifically logical to leave the introduction without explaining the reasons.

Otherwise, why did the researcher choose to study the idea of his research topic?

Why did he go through all the trouble and spend money, effort, time, research, investigation, and scrutiny?

So, the element of choosing the reasons for the introduction is necessary to clarify the status of the proposed idea and the seriousness and importance of dealing with it as a new idea that can be studied and researched.

Sometimes, the research idea is exhausted and not worth studying.

However, the researcher's style and his use of some exciting scientific terms and his way of presenting the importance of that idea force the reader to complete reading the research without being satisfied with only part of it.

In other words, it is a logical justification and a narrative description of the importance of the topic.

2. Presenting the Research Problem and How to Solve It:

It is best for every comprehensive introduction to include a presentation of the research problem.

This means addressing the problem that hinders the application of the idea or the problem that the study entails overall.

It could be a social problem that the study addressed, an economic problem, or highlighting a legal loophole or a political issue that may need to be resolved.

The researcher then presents the problem and then shows the tools to solve it.

Often, some research papers review a vital problem worth studying, but the same study does not provide solutions in its content.

Here, the study has addressed part of the elements of scientific research and left the most important part, which is solving the problem or at least making recommendations for solving the problem.

Of course, this depends on the researcher's specialization in the topic of his research paper.

Here, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of specialization in studying any problem that is raised for discussion or study.

Introduction Elements:

1. Scope and Community:

It is important to emphasize the identification of the study community, and the problem should not be general.

By identifying the study community, we can provide a large part of the solutions.

The scope of the study is an important element of the introduction.

By scope, we mean either geographical boundaries, which applies to (identifying the study community). It is best to specify which community we are studying. As it is known, each community has its own customs, traditions, and ways of life and livelihood, some of which differ radically from other communities.

Therefore, the difference in the nature of the life of those peoples is also reflected in the nature of the diagnosis of the research problem and, consequently, the nature and bases of the solutions.

Or temporal (historical) boundaries, and it should not be general because each time and period has its own characteristics and specific study methodology.

Therefore, events and people cannot apply the criteria specific to a particular time or historical period to other periods. This is one of the common mistakes that many researchers make.

2. Research Methodology:

There are many different research methodologies, and they vary depending on the type and nature of the study.

Each specialization has a scientific writing methodology that is completely different from the other specialization.

This naturally applies even to the same specialization, and I mean by that (scientific specializations) and (human specializations).

The research methodology is a path or a methodological work plan that accompanies the work of researchers and specialized writers exclusively.

A non-specialist can follow any method they see fit because their product does not represent a specific field of specialization, and therefore, constructive scientific criticism cannot be directed to such studies, and I mean by that non-specialized studies.

Perhaps among the most prominent of these methods are the descriptive method, the narrative method, and the analytical method.

3. Reviewing Previous Studies:

Shedding light on the analysis and review of previous studies in a specific cognitive field is an important element of writing the introduction.

The question that arises is, what is the benefit of reviewing previous studies?

To answer, we say that the benefit of reviewing those studies is to show the researcher's ability to address a scientific idea that had been raised some time ago by other researchers.

In some cases, some ideas are exhausted and have been thoroughly researched, but why does the researcher come to raise such an idea again?

So, it is to show the researcher's ability to address the previous idea but in a new, logical, and scientific style with completely new research tools, such as analytical or statistical analysis tools or sources and references so that the researcher with the new idea can present new results that differ completely, not partially, from the results reached by researchers before him who studied the same topic.

Here, the good researcher is distinguished from the researcher who does not possess the most prominent features and tools of scientific research.

4. Questions and Hypotheses:

Here the researcher raises a set of hypotheses and questions that arouse the reader's desire to complete reading the study to find out the answers to those questions.

It is best for every competent researcher to formulate those questions in an exciting and stimulating way, using terms and sentences that reach all recipients, taking into account the individual differences in understanding them and responding to their data within what is presented in the folds of the research.

These hypotheses are one of the most important elements of writing the introduction.

Conclusion of Scientific Research: Importance and Elements

The conclusion of a research paper is one of the main parts of any solid scientific project. In it, the researcher shows the most prominent results and recommendations that he reached in his study project. In it, the final features of the study become clear, and the skill of the writer and his ability to understand his subject and the extent of his interaction with the ideas that he reached, which were the subject of the idea of his project, are evident.

Not only that, but his ability to analyze the most important points that his research stopped at and present them to the reader in an easy and logical style, far from what we can call the cost of narrating and analyzing the concept, with the presentation of new proposals presented by the researcher to the reader or to anyone who embarks on the experience of the same idea that the researcher experienced.

The conclusion is the last station in the researcher's work journey after a long and arduous work journey that he dealt with in the project of the idea of his study through logical, scientific, and analytical methods far from forgery and distortion. In the conclusion stage, he had gained scientific experience and was familiar with integrated research tools that included all aspects of his study.

Therefore, he provided many people with a set of recommendations and presented the essence of his long effort to everyone looking for tools to use to explore the same idea but comprehensively. In one way or another, it is part of the strength of the research, and it is impossible to ignore not paying attention to it or writing it in the correct way according to the known scientific standards.

The content and form of the conclusion differ according to the diversity and diversity of scientific disciplines and according to the methodology followed in the research. The researcher must choose from among all the forms of scientific methodologies, according to his specialization, the type of conclusion that suits the idea he studied.

Everyone knows that the tools of analysis and inference differ according to the specialties. For example, the results in the human specialization are completely different from the results in the scientific or applied specialties.

Also, the means and tools of analysis and outputs differ depending on the specialization, as we mentioned previously.

A very important point that I would like to clarify is that the results included in the conclusion certainly differ in their format, presentation, and context according to the topic raised for discussion or study.

If the topic deals with a single specific idea, the results will be one and specific, centered around that idea. It is easier for the researcher to deal with several axes or several points and then try to put results and a conclusion for them and analyze each scientific issue separately.

This matter requires a time cost, if we may call it, and a material cost and double effort. Therefore, I do not think that the results will come in the required form if we compare those results with the results of the topic with the single idea.

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